

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MEDICINALLY IMPORTANT PLANTS OF GARAGUSH MOUNTAIN

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Abstract

The Garagush Mountain system, which is one of the highest peaks of the Deraleaz range, has rich vegetation. Garagush Mountain is of great importance as it hosts more than 800 plant species. Thus, the rich vegetation includes species of more than 80 families. These, in turn, are food, medicine, decorative, fodder, etc. includes important species. These plants, which can be used in folk medicine, in pharmacies, in the preparation of medicinal preparations, in the form of tea and infusions, are the "healing and care" that nature has given us. Medicinal plants widely used by the population in the study area were discovered by us. Among them, we can mention the species of *Berberis*, *Crataegus*, *Rosa*, *Thymus* and *Cephalaria*.

Keywords: Garagush Mountain, medicinal plants, *Berberis vulgaris* L., *Crataegus pentagyna* Waldst.&Kit., *Rosa corymbifera* Borkh., *Thymus nummularius* Bieb., *Cephalaria nachiczewanica* Borb..

The Garagush Mountain system, which is one of the highest peaks of the Deraleaz range, has rich vegetation. Garagush Mountain is of great importance as it hosts more than 800 plant species. Thus, the rich vegetation includes species of more than 80 families. These, in turn, are food, medicine, decorative, fodder, etc. includes important species. The direction I would like to draw your attention to is the medicinally important species of Garagush Mountain. This corner of Azerbaijan, which has a mysterious and colorful nature, is of special importance from both the economic and the medical point of view. These plants, which can be used in folk medicine, in pharmacies, in the preparation of medicinal preparations, in the form of tea and infusions, are the "healing and care" that nature has given us. These plants are useful and useful in the treatment of most diseases, even in the prevention of those diseases.

Medicinal plants widely used by the population in the study area were discovered by us. Among them, we can mention the species of *Berberis*, *Crataegus*, *Rosa*, *Thymus* and *Cephalaria*.

Berberidaceae Juss. familia's 2 species of *Berberis* L. genus spread of in the Garagush Mountain area: *Berberis densiflora* Boiss.&Buhse and *B. vulgaris* L.. The mentioned species of *Berberis* grow in forests, thickets, riverbanks, slopes with mixed trees-shrubs-mixed-foot, roadsides and fences. It is widely used by people for its crimson, pink, whitish, black cluster fruits, attractive yellow flowers, attractive appearance, and most importantly, its edible fruits. The fruits of all types of *Berberis* are eaten by the population, they are dried and used as a spice at any time of the year, compote and jam are made, tea is brewed and used for blood pressure. However, the most industrially important of the species of *Berberis* is the common *B. vulgaris* L.

Berberis vulgaris L. is a shrub 2-3 m high. The bark of young branches is yellowish-brown or yellowish-gray, and the bark of old branches is gray. The leaves are usually three-crossed, 2 cm long. The thorns are hard, sharp and hard, sometimes they are located singly on the branches. The light-green leaves are thin, egg-shaped or inverted, sometimes lancet-shaped,

shiny on the upper side, and clearly distinguished net veins on the lower side. The leaves are obtuse at the tip and wedge-shaped at the base, the edges are ciliated and saw-toothed. 15-20 flowers are light-yellow and collected in bunches. The berry is oblong, 12 mm long and reddish in color. The taste is very sour. It has 2-3 seeds. It blooms in May-June, and ripens in September-October.

In the area of Garagush Mountain, *Berberis vulgaris* L. is found in sparse forests, thickets and river valleys at altitudes of 1100 - 2300 m above sea level. It grows singly or in groups in areas where it spreads. Sometimes it forms dense forests. *Berberis vulgaris* L. is resistant to heat, cold and frost. *Berberis vulgaris* L. leaves, fruits and roots are used. It is a food, dye and medicinal plant. It is repellent and bloodthirsty. It increases blood clotting, lowers blood pressure, reduces the number of heart attacks and has a calming effect. *Berberis vulgaris* L. leaf is also given as part of "biliary tea". Its fruit juice is used in high fever, as a diuretic, in digestive disorders, in anorexia, and in the treatment of diabetes. *Berberis vulgaris* L. fruit is used in folk medicine to treat scurvy, rickets, anemia, fever, and gastrointestinal diseases. Jam is used in the treatment of jaundice. *Berberinum sulfate* preparation in tablet form is prepared from it. Unlike other species, the natural resource of *Berberis vulgaris* L. is relatively abundant.

5 species belonging to *Rosa* L. genus of Rosaceae family were found in the area. *Rosa sosnovskyana* Tamamsch. [VU A2cd; B1b(iii)c(ii)], *Rosa rapinii* Boiss. & Honey. (VU D1) and *Rosa tuschetica* Boiss. [VU B1b(iii,iv)c(ii)] is protected by statuses [4, p.17-18]. *Rosa canina* L. and *Rosa corymbifera* Borkh. the natural reserve of species is relatively abundant.

Rose is a perennial shrub that grows wild. People call it *wild rose*. The *Rose* bush can reach a height of 1.5 - 2.5 meters. Branches branch out from the sides of its trunk, and small leaves grow densely on top of the branches. *Rose* are located at the tip of baby green pods. Berries begin to form after the flowers of the rose fall. *Rose* flowers are light pink or pink in color, have five petals and measure 5 cm in diameter. It blooms in May-

June, and after the flowers fall, it is replaced by elongated berries with many small hairs. These berries ripen in September–October.

Rose seeds are rich in fatty acids and vitamins. Infusion of rose fruit or root is very useful for the body. This infusion is rich in polyvitamins. The infusion has a choleric, diuretic, depressant effect on the body. Brewing strengthens the walls of blood vessels, increases the amount of red blood cells, increases immunity, improves metabolism, memory, stimulates the function of sex hormones, cures colds and flu, and relieves headaches. Rose are widely used in folk medicine. It is used in the prevention of avitaminosis, hypovitaminosis, infectious diseases. It has a bat healing effect. It is very useful to drink its infusion during burns and injuries. Rose eliminates the symptoms of atherosclerosis, accelerates the regeneration of damaged tissues. For these reasons, it is very useful to drink a decoction of Rose during dermatoses and trophic wounds.

Ripe Rose contain proteins, carbohydrates, fibers, free organic acids, a large amount of minerals (potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, iron, manganese, chromium, molybdenum, cobalt, etc.), vitamins (B1, B2, B6, K, RE, PP, C), dyes, carotene, riboflavin, citric and malic acid, sugar, phytoncides and essential oils. The amount of vitamin C contained in rose is 5-10 times more than black currant and 40 times more than lemon. The infusion of rose cleans the blood-vascular system, improves metabolism, eliminates anemia, and cures kidney, bladder, and liver diseases. Rose infusion is very effective in treating scurvy. Roses are widely used in folk medicine for general strengthening, toning, reducing the symptoms of atherosclerosis, increasing the body's resistance to infectious diseases.

Another species belonging to the family of *Rosaceae* Juss. is the *Crataegus* genus, many species of which have been discovered by us in the area. Mainly *Crataegus meyeri* Pojark., *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq., *Crataegus orientalis* Pall. & Bieb., *Crataegus pentagyna* Waldst. & Kit. and *Crataegus pontica* C. Koch. species are abundant in nature.

Crataegus pentagyna Waldst.&Kit. is a small gray-barked, thin-thorned tree or shrub with a branched trunk. The leaves are egg-shaped, 3-7-lobed, the base is wedge-shaped, and the upper side is dark green. The flowers are collected in a complex flower group on the shield. The flower crown is white. The fruit is inside, the color turns black when ripe, the lat part is red, and it has 3-5 smooth kernels. The plant blooms in May, and fruits ripen in August–September. *Crataegus pentagyna* is common in forests, thickets, and river valleys. Sometimes it also forms dense forests. Flowers and fruits of *Crataegus pentagyna* are used medicinally. Its flowers are harvested in May, and its fruits are harvested in August–September when they are fully ripe [2, 80-81]. An infusion, tincture and extract are prepared from its fruits and flowers, and it is widely used as a medicine to regulate heart activity after acute angina and flu, as well as to reduce blood pressure in functional disorders of heart activity - angina pectoris, arrhythmia, hypertension, insomnia, cardiac neurosis. The substance "Kratemon" (*Crataemon*), obtained from

Crataegus pentagyna, is used in the absence of coronary vessels. Liquid extract of hawthorn fruits is included in the composition of "Cardiovalen" drug. In the sources of Azerbaijani folk medicine, *Crataegus pentagyna* is used in the treatment of anemia, heart palpitations, blood pressure and measles.

Three species of *Thymus* of Lamiaceae family were found in the area. These are *Thymus nummularius* Bieb., *Thymus rariflorus* C.Koch and *Thymus kotschyanus* Boiss.&Hohen. types. Its height is from 20 cm to 35 cm. It is a small, fragrant half-bush. The gills are thin, brown, creeping. The base is covered with a dark brown bark, often rooting and forming additional roots. The leaves are small, oblong or elliptical, short-stalked or sessile. The flowers are small, pink or purple-pink in color, double-lipped, sparsely gathered in a flower head. The fruit is dry, divided into four nuts. *Thymus* blooms in June–July, the fruit ripens in August–September. It reproduces by seeds and vegetatively. It can last up to 30 years.

The green above-ground part of *thymus* is harvested when the plant blooms or before. *Thymus* is widely used in cooking (especially canning), as well as in the cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. One of the most widely used fields of *thymus* is medicine. *Thymus* helps to relieve lung, bronchial, stomach and intestinal problems. It is used in the form of tea and gargle for cough and inflammation of the upper respiratory tract. Regulates blood circulation, lowers blood sugar, plays an effective role against intestinal parasites. *Thymus*, which has an antiseptic effect, is also widely used in skin problems. It is widely used in skin, nervous disorders and muscle spasms. This substance is also very good for neuritis, seborrheic dermatitis and glossitis. This plant, which also has a diuretic effect, protects the body from aging and eliminates convulsions.

The genus *Cephalaria* of *Caprifoliaceae* Juss. family is a widely distributed medicinal plant in Azerbaijan. Most species of *Cephalaria* are perennial herbs with attractive yellow flowers. There are 60 species of *Cephalaria* in the world, 12 of which grow in Azerbaijan. *Cephalaria nachiczewanica* Borb. type was discovered in the area. The flowers and roots of the plant are widely used in folk medicine. The flowers of the plant have been used as an infusion (tea) since ancient times for colds, internal bleeding, as well as cardiovascular and kidney-urinary tract diseases. This flower is called "Solmaz flower" due to the fact that the bright yellow flowers retain their beauty for years after being collected. This plant has a choleric effect. It also stimulates the secretion of pancreatic juice [6, p.301-302].

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